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Influence of Guidance and Counselling Services on the Academic Performance of Male and Female Students in Rivers State Universities.

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to examine Influence of Guidance and Counselling Services on the Academic Performance of Male and Female Students in Rivers State Universities. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. A descriptive Survey research design was adopted in the study. The population of the study comprised of 160 respondents. The entire population was studied. The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled “Questionnaire on Guidance and Counselling Services on the Academic Performance of Male and Female Students (QGCSAPS)”. It was designed on a 4-Point rating scale of High Extent (HE), Moderate Extent (ME), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE). Test-re-test method was used for the reliability test which yielded reliability co-efficient 0.74. Mean and standard deviation were used in analyzing the research questions. The findings revealed that Guidance and counselling services influences academic performance of male and female students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. It was therefore recommended that Guidance and counselling coordinators in tertiary institutions should intensify more actions on how to improve academic performance of students.

Keywords: Guidance and Counselling, counseling services and Academic Performance.

INTRODUCTION

The terms “guidance” and “counseling” have been used either individually or synonymously by various scholars. As a result, many text interchangeably used the term guidance for counseling and counseling for guidance the general consensus among the specialists is that guidance is a family name for all the helping services within the general educational and community services. Guidance is a common language that involves a personal help given by someone; it is designed to assist a person to decide where he wants to go; what he wants to do, or how he can best accomplish his purpose; it assist him to solve problems that arise in his life (Ibok, Thomas, & Okri, 2025; Akpa, Ekpenyong, & Emmanuel, 2024; Ibok, Ushinyin, Masor, Unoh, Etura, & Udobong, 2023).

Counselling is a very important aspect of students’ life as it enables them to get assistance and directions on their areas of worries and concerns by interacting with professional counselors who are knowledgeable on the areas that students have concerns as it will hem to get right direction that they need in the regard. There are significant roles that counselors play in the molding the lives of individuals especially students in various tertiary institutions irrespective of their gender (Bakare,2021). Counselors provide professional

guidance to students at various level of education especially tertiary institutions because the students at this level of education are usually at a very sensitive stage of their life where major decisions are taken. These decisions can either make or destroy the life choice of these students if they are not properly guided by counsellors that have vast knowledge in the areas of concern. However, it is also important to note that the gender of a student plays significant role in their individual choices and perceptions of certain issues and academic performances too.

Guidance and counseling are essential in tertiary institutions for students' development and academic performance. If a tertiary institution lacks effective guidance and counseling, students are denied advice on how to manage and deal with their emotional conflict and personal problems (Ibrahim, Aloka, Wambiya & Raburu, 2024). They are therefore assisted on how to deal with psychological problems which likely to affect their academic performance. Other than just teaching students in the school curriculum, counselors also solve psychological and behavior problems. Students are today having more misconduct problems than it was being experienced some years ago (Lai-Yeung, 2024). This has been as a result of intensive exposure to modern technology.

Guidance plays a vital role in removing the educational, personal, social, mental, emotional and other similar problems of the students. Guidance as a term refers to a broad area of educational activities and services aimed at assisting individuals in making and carrying out adequate plans leading to achievement of desired life, (Gibson,2018). It is meant to equip the individual (student) with knowledge and techniques that will enable him or her to identify and find ways of anticipating and solving problems including academic performance. Guidance and counselling services also helps to facilitate development of effective study habits, motivation, identifying learning or subject related problems, helping students to see the relevance of school years in life and for future, developing skills, right attitude and interests to help making a choice in career. Guidance and counseling, thus, promotes holistic development of every student. Counselling is the skilled and principled use of relationships that provides self-knowledge, emotional acceptance and lead to personal growth. It is more concerned with addressing and resolving specific problems such as making decisions, coping with crises, working through feelings and inner conflicts or improving relationships with others. It is a process in which the helper expresses care and concern towards the person with a problem so as to facilitate that person's personal growth and positive change through self-understanding. Guidance and counselling is concerned with individuals' behavioral processes. However, the two terms can be looked at differently. Many authors have defined counselling differently though they all agreed on some basic facts. Kiriswa (2018), renowned counsellor defines counselling as an enabling process designed to help an individual come to terms with his or her life as it is, and ultimately reach a greater maturity through learning to take responsibility and to make informed decisions on academic performance. Guidance and Counseling is a professional field which has a broad range of activities and services aimed at assisting individuals to understand themselves, others, school environment and attain abilities to adjust accordingly. As individuals develop through stages of life and educational attainment, they encounter problems, challenges and conflict situations. These individuals also need to develop value systems, make decisions, set goals and work towards them. All these cannot be achieved without self-understanding and decision-making skills, which are not innate, but need to be developed. The need to address these challenges and to promote educational success and healthy life therefore, call for exposure to guidance and counselling programs by individuals/students as a way of promoting academic performance (Kiriswa, 2018). Guidance and counselling is therefore designed to help individuals/students in their different problems and concerns, so that they grow up well-adjusted individuals capable not only of living productive lives, but are also prepared to contribute their quota to the development of their society. Gibson (2018) states that Guidance and counselling services prepare students to assume increasing responsibility for their decisions and grow in their ability to understand and accept the results of their choices including academic performance. There are different aspects of guidance and counselling such as family guidance and counselling, marriage guidance and counselling and pastoral guidance and counselling among others. Denga (2021), referred to the guidance and counselling services as "cluster of formalized educational services designed by the school to assist

students to achieve self-knowledge or self-understanding and academic performance which is necessary for them to attain the fullest self-development and self-realization of their potential". These services include: student appraisal service, information service, counselling service, placement service, orientation service, referral service, follow-up, evaluation service, and research service. Appraisal service involves the use of tests and non-test instruments to collect, analyze and interpret data on students to understand themselves better. It also affords counsellors and significant others, the opportunity of having insight into the strengths and weaknesses of students. Information service is tailored towards equipping students with the necessary information in the areas of educational, vocational and personal-social. This information is very important because they assist students to make wise decisions about life. Counselling service is a face to face interaction between the counsellor and the students, through which students are assisted towards overcoming obstacles to their academic, vocational, personal-social progress and other life needs. Placement service is concerned with assisting students to adjust to the next stage of development whether in school or on the job. Orientation service is designed to familiarize fresh students with their environment. It is a process of initiating an individual to a work or learning situation and of instructing him about rules, regulations and responsibilities, as an introduction to a new situation. Referral service affords the school counsellor an opportunity to refer the cases which he cannot handle to specialists like clinical psychologist, medical practitioner and others. Follow-up, evaluation services are designed to ascertain the extent to which the guidance programme previously carried out by the school is meeting the objectives for which it was established and also to monitor the progress of students in their work places. Research service helps the school counsellor to discover relevant information that can improve students' learning and understanding. The services should be an on-going process which professional counsellors should embrace and encourage. These services constitute the core of any guidance program and should be organised to facilitate the growth and development of all students from kindergarten through post high school experiences (Erford, 2020; Erford, 2021; Neukrug, 2021).

Academic performance refers to how well a student is accomplishing his or her tasks and studies (Scottt's, 2022). Grades are certainly the most well-known indicator of academic performance. Grades are the student's "score" for their classes and overall tenure. Grades are most often a tallying or average of assignment and test scores and may often be affected by factors such as attendance an instructor opinion of the student as well. According to Ward, Stocker and Murray-Ward (2026) academic performance refers to the outcome of education; the extent to which the student, teacher or institution have achieved their educational goals. Academic performance is the ability to study and remember facts and being able to communicate one's knowledge verbally or written on paper (Answers, 2020). Academic performance refers to the extent to which students have achieved mastery of the objectives of the subjects they are exposed to in school. According to (Aremu & Sokan 2023) Academic performance has been observed in tertiary institution subjects. The blame for poor academic performance among secondary school students could be attributable to a variety of factors such as student inability to manage their time, peers influence, family factors and the likes. Parents, teachers, curriculum, experts and evaluators have expressed considerable concern over the deteriorating students' performance in public secondary schools. Guidance is a rudimentary ingredient that plays a crucial role in school system and insists on upholding the social and moral values of students.

Statement of the Problem

Guidance and Counselling as a concept has existed since the beginning of human society. Guidance and counselling programmes in educational institutions are designed to provide professional relationships between counsellors and students and intended to guide, direct and assist students to solve their problems as well as develop their potentials including the academic performance of student irrespective of their gender. Poor academic performances among tertiary institutions students is of a great concern, this has a negative influence on the various programmes in tertiary institutions. This particular circumstance is of a great concern to stakeholders who always see students performing poorly in their academics. This can be traced to certain situations that the male or female students is going through which may not be voiced out except through the intervention of a professional guidance and counselling expert who provides guidance

and counselling services to these students. It is on this ground that this study seeks to determine the influence of Guidance and Counseling services on Academic Performance of Students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Purpose of the study

The main purpose of this study was to determine the Influence of Guidance and Counseling services on Academic Performance of Students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the influence of Guidance and Counseling services on Academic Performance of male Students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.
2. Determine the influence of Guidance and Counseling services on Academic Performance of female Students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

1. To what extent does Guidance and Counseling services influence Academic Performance of male Students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?
2. To what extent does Guidance and Counseling services influence Academic Performance of female Students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?

METHOD

The study examined the Influence of Guidance and Counseling services on Academic Performance of Students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State. A descriptive survey research design was adopted. Two research objectives with two research questions guided the study. Population of the study consisted of 180 students in selected tertiary institutions. The Instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire validated by three experts, two from Guidance and counselling and one from measurement and evaluation. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to test the reliability of the instrument and a reliability coefficient of 0.84 was obtained. Mean and standard deviation were used to analyze research questions. The instrument for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled Questionnaire on Influence of Guidance and Counseling services on Academic Performance of Students in tertiary institutions (QIGCSAPSTI). The instrument was structured on a four-point scale of High Extent (HE), Moderate Extent (ME), Low Extent (LE) and Very Low Extent (VLE).

RESULTS

Research Question: *To what extent does Guidance and Counseling services influence Academic Performance of male Students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?*

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Extent Guidance and Counseling services influence Academic Performance of male Students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

S/N	ITEMS	\bar{X}	SD	RMK
6.	Male students are allowed to have voluntary visits to counsellors as a way of increasing their academic performance.	3.78	0.76	HE
7.	Counsellors encourages male students to have positive attitude towards learning.	3.51	0.70	HE
8.	Counsellors assists male students to develop high aspirations towards their	3.88	0.78	HE

9.	academic pursuits. Counsellors encourages male students to have positive attitude towards learning.	3.77	0.75	HE
10.	Counsellors assists male students to develop effective interpersonal relationship skills to improve academic performance.	3.76	0.75	HE
Total Mean/SD		18.70	3.74	
Grand Mean/SD		3.74	0.75	

The response in Table shows that; Male students are allowed to have voluntary visits to counsellors as a way of increasing their academic performance, Counsellors encourages male students to have positive attitude towards learning, Counsellors assists male students to develop high aspirations towards their academic pursuits, Counsellors encourages male students to have positive attitude towards learning and Counsellors assists male students to develop effective interpersonal relationship skills to improve academic performance at a high extent. This indicates guidance and counselling services influences academic performance of male students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

Research Question 2: *To what extent does Guidance and Counseling services influence Academic Performance of female Students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State?*

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Extent Guidance And Counseling Services Influence Academic Performance Of Female Students In Tertiary Institutions In Rivers State

S/N	ITEMS	\bar{X}	SD	RMK
6.	Provision of information in the selection of courses in tertiary institution influence Academic Performance of female Students .	3.62	0.72	HE
7.	Counsellor educates female students on how to form successful collaboration after school.	3.57	0.71	HE
8.	Counselors assists female students to enroll in the most appropriate academic course work.	3.77	0.75	HE
9.	Female students are assisted by counselors in the choice of courses.	3.68	0.74	HE
11.	Counsellor provides information to female students that increases their professional knowledge	3.62	0.72	HE
Total Mean/SD		18.26	3.64	
Grand Mean/SD		3.65	0.73	

Source: Field Survey, 2026

The responses in Table 2 shows that; Provision of information in the selection of courses in tertiary institution influence Academic Performance of female Students, Counsellor educates female students on how to form successful collaboration after school, Counselors assists female students to enroll in the most appropriate academic course work, Female students are assisted by counselors in the choice of courses and Counsellor provides information to female students that increases their professional knowledge at a high extent. This indicates guidance and counselling services influences academic performance of female students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The discussion in this study was done according to the findings of this study.

Findings from table one shows that; Male students are allowed to have voluntary visits to counsellors as a way of increasing their academic performance, Counsellors encourages male students to have positive attitude towards learning, Counsellors assists male students to develop high aspirations towards their academic pursuits, Counsellors encourages male students to have positive attitude towards learning and Counsellors assists male students to develop effective interpersonal relationship skills to improve academic performance at a high extent.

The finding is in line with the view of Okeke (2023) who opined that appraisal services of guidance and counselling affords the counsellors the opportunity of having insight into the strength and weakness of students academically.

The findings in table two shows that; Provision of information in the selection of courses in tertiary institution influence Academic Performance of female Students, Counsellor educates female students on how to form successful collaboration after school, Counselors assists female students to enroll in the most appropriate academic course work, Female students are assisted by counselors in the choice of courses and Counsellor provides information to female students that increases their professional knowledge at a high extent.

The findings are in line with the view of Okeke (2023) who opined that appraisal services of guidance and counselling affords the counsellors the opportunity of having insight into the strength and weakness of students academically.

CONCLUSION

From the data analysis and findings, it was concluded that; Guidance and counselling services influences academic performance of male and female students in tertiary institutions in Rivers State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the study recommendations that:

1. Guidance and counselling coordinators in tertiary institutions should intensify more actions on how to improve academic performance of students.
2. Professional guidance and counselling coordinators should introduce more counselling Services in tertiary institutions.

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